

Controlled Manipulation of TRAIL into Single Human Colon Cancer Cells Using Atomic Force Microscope

Yingmin Qu, Jinyun Liu, Guoliang Wang,
Zhengxun Song and Zuobin Wang*

CNM & JR3CN,
Changchun University of Science and Technology,
Jilin, China

*Corresponding author: wangz@cust.edu.cn

Zuobin Wang

JR3CN & IRAC,

University of Bedfordshire,
Luton LU1 3JU, United Kingdom

Abstract—In this study, an AFM tip was used to penetrate the human colon cancer cells (SW480) in the culture medium containing pEGFP-N1-TRAIL plasmids. The trail plasmids encoded with the enhanced green fluorescent protein (EGFP) were moved into the SW480 cells through membrane holes created by the AFM probe. Following the penetration, the culture medium was changed into the RPMI1640 medium supplemented with 10% of fetal bovine serum and incubated for 24h. The expression of PEGFP-N1-TRAIL in SW480 cells was then observed by inverted fluorescence microscope. The experiment results indicate that the AFM tip can be used to penetrate the membranes of targeted cells individually.

Keywords—TRAIL, human colon cancer cells, atomic force microscope

I. INTRODUCTION

Gene delivery technologies include biological, chemical and physical approaches, and they are very important for understanding the effect of a particular gene on cells. Hahn et al reported that antitumor endogenous inhibitor was carried by retroviral and adenoviral vectors. In a vivo experiment, a tumor volume was decreased to 70% compared with the control group [1]. Although the adenovirus infection has high efficiency, it can trigger the inflammatory response [2]. The physical transfection methods such as the microinjection and electroporation have also been introduced [3,4]. The microinjection with microcapillaries could cause the significant damage because of the larger diameter than AFM tip. Electroporation is a traditional method with low accuracy [5]. Carrier-mediated transfection was reported in previous studies. Carbon nanotube spearing method was investigated to carry the exogenous DNA into the cells by Cai et al. Their results revealed the transfection efficiency in B-lymphoma and primary neurons [6]. O' Brien et al. found a new method based on a gene gun to deliver the DNA and dyes into the cells efficiently [7]. Wu et al developed single-walled carbon nanotubes modified with a DNA probe as a carrier to deliver molecules into living cells [8]. But the method is not suitable for single cells. In addition, the carrier may be complex compound with high toxicity for living cells.

Since the discovery in 1986 [9], AFM has played an important role in many areas such as material science, physics, chemistry and biology with its specific functions that have

attracted particular attention [10,11]. The AFM tip can be used for the manipulation of living cells such as penetration and injection. Han et al. investigated the gene delivery using a nanoneedle coated with green fluorescent protein DNA. Then the green fluorescent protein with the target gene was expressed in the cell nucleus [12]. Because of the high therapeutic effect and low toxicity, tumor necrosis factor (TNF)-related apoptosis-inducing ligand (TRAIL) was used for anti-cancer. Some cancer cells were induced apoptosis by trail gene function [13-15].

In this study, the controlled manipulation of TRAIL into single human colon cancer cells were carried out using an atomic force microscope (AFM) tip. It caused less damage on the cells because the diameter of the tip was only 10nm approximately. The recombinant plasmids containing the trail fragment into the single SW480 cells resulted in cell apoptosis because of the effect of trail gene.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Recombinant plasmids construction

The sequences of primers for trail were 5'-CTCGAGATGGTGAGAGAAAGAGGTCCTCAGAGAGT-3' (sense) and 5'-GGATCCCGGCCAACTAAAAAGGCCCGC-3' (anti-sense). The PCR condition was 94°C for 3 min followed by 30 cycles at 94°C for 30 s, 56°C for 30 s and 72°C for 30s. The PCR production was detected by 0.8% agarose gel and purified with a DNA purification kit. The production was ligation with the pMD18-T simple vector and then transformed into the E. coli DH5 α . The plasmids were extracted by DNA Extraction Kit.

The recombinant plasmids named pEGFP-N1-TRAIL for the expression of the green fluorescent protein were prepared. The pMD18T-TRAIL was digested with the restriction endonuclease XhoI and BamHI, and then the pEGFP-N1 vector was also digested with XhoI and BamHI. In order to construct the recombinant plasmids pEGFP-N1-TRAIL, the vector fragment of pEGFP-N1 and target gene fragment of trail were linked with T4 DNA ligase (TAKARA, Japan). The linked production was evaluated by PCR and restriction endonuclease digestion identification through 0.8% agarose gel electrophoresis. The candidate recombinant plasmids were

further identified by sequence analysis with automatic DNA sequencer.

B. Cell culture

Human colon cancer (SW480) cells were plated on the coverslips coated by poly-L-Lysine (Sigma, Germany) with the final concentration of 0.01mg/ml and cultured with RPMI1640 medium (Hyclone, USA), supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) at 37°C in 5% CO₂ incubator. The SW480 cells were allowed to grow on the coverslips up to 50% before transfection experiments. The coverslips with SW480 cells were washed three times with PBS (137mM NaCl, 2.7mM KCl, 10mM NaH₂PO₄, 2mM KH₂PO₄) and used for AFM experiments under physiological conditions.

C. Transfection experiments

The penetration experiments were performed with an AFM. The AFM is suitable for the manipulation of biological samples in the culture medium. The AFM combined with an optical microscope was used in this study. The force feedback can be obtained from the AFM system. The AFM tip was used to penetrate into the single cells. The experiments were made by a silicon probe (Budget Sensors, ContAl-G) with the cantilever length of 450µm, the width of 50µm, the tip radius of 10nm, the thickness of 2µm, the resonance frequency of 13kHz and the nominal spring constant of 0.2N/m. In the experiment, SW480 cells were cultured in the medium with 50% pEGFP-N1-TRAIL recombinant plasmids. The AFM tip was used to create holes on the cell membrane. After the AFM tip lowered into the cell membrane for 1 min, then retrieved from the cell surface. After the procedure, the cells were rinsed with PBS and further cultured in RPMI1640 medium supplemented with 10% FBS in the CO₂ incubator.

D. Fluorescence observed

Twenty-four hours after the penetration into the cell membrane with the AFM tip, the fluorescence images were obtained by inverted fluorescence microscope (NIS-F, Nikon, Japan). The fluorescence microscope analysis was carried out using a green fluorescence detector with an excitation wavelength of 488nm and an emission wavelength of 525nm. The images were analyzed using the software (Ti-S).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Identification of recombinant plasmids pEGFP-N1-TRAIL

Recombinant plasmids pEGFP-N1-TRAIL were verified by amplification (Fig.1a) and restriction endonuclease digestion (Fig.1b) with electrophoresis. From Fig. 1a, according to the DNA marker 2000bp, the target gene shows 500bp approximately. The pEGFP-N1-TRAIL plasmids digestion with XhoI and BamHI show two bands in lanes 1 and 2 (Fig. 1b) in which the higher one was the pEGFP-N1 plasmids and the lower one was the trail gene (about 500bp). Then the recombinant plasmids were analyzed by DNA sequencer. Alignment of this cDNA sequence with the human trail gene from genetic library revealed 100% identity, confirming that the trail plasmids were successfully inserted into the pEGFP-N1 vector (Fig.2).

Fig.1 (a) PCR of TRAIL gene; (b) Restriction analysis of recombinant plasmids

Fig.2 Alignment of the recombinants with genetic library

B. Gene delivery of trail recombinant plasmids into SW480 cells

The AFM was combined with an inverted microscope to manipulate the cells with high positioning accuracy (Fig.3a). The morphologies of SW480 cells were observed clearly with the AFM (Fig.3b). Obataya et al. investigated the mechanical response between the nano-needle and HEK293 cells. The fabricated sharp tip was penetrated into the cell membrane accompanied with a leap on the force-distance curves [16]. In this work, when the tip was indented into the cell, the force feedback can be monitored, as shown in Fig.3(c). The tip indentation force was shown approximately 1.5nN. Hategan et al. [17] reported the cell membrane penetration force was about 1-3nN, and Obataya et al. [16] investigated that the force for penetration into the erythrocytes was about 10-30nN. The different indentation force values depend on the type of the targeted cells and the AFM tip geometry. But it is important to choose the suitable penetration force to avoid the significant damage on the cell viability. The recombinant plasmids were moved into the SW480 cells through the holes on the cell membrane created with the AFM probe, which was consistent with the literature reported by Afrin et al. [18]. Their results show that the phospholipase A₂ coated bead mounted on the AFM cantilever can be used to observe the

intracellular structure. After indentation on the cell surface approximately 5-10min, the holes were created with the diameter of 5-10 μ m.

Fig.3 (a) Optical image of the AFM tip and SW480 cells; (b) AFM image of the SW480 cells; (c) Force-distance curve after indentation into the cell surface.

C. Detection of recombinant plasmids expression with inverted fluorescence microscope

This study shows that the SW480 cells can be successfully penetrated by AFM tip. Fluorescence images were taken 24h after the penetration of single SW480 cells. The green fluorescence can be observed in the SW480 cells after injection (Fig.4). Cuerrier et al. [19] reported that the fluorescence can be observed after the decorated tip indentation of the eukaryotic cells for 24, 48, and 72h. After the plasmids were transfected into the cells, the cellular behavior, morphological changes and signal transduction inside the cells can be observed with fluorescence markers.

Fig.4 Fluorescence images of the W480 cells after transfection with pEGFP-N1-TRAIL.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, human colon cancer cells were transfected with the recombinant plasmids pEGFP-N1-TRAIL encoding for the fluorescence protein EGFP using the AFM probe. The force leap and fluorescence images showed that the AFM tip was successfully penetrated into the living cells. The target gene was expressed in the cell nucleus after the penetration of the cell membrane for 24h. This work provides a method for the delivery of gene into living cells especially for the difficult transfection cells to study the cell behavior. It can be used for precise manipulations or analyses of cells for the prevention, diagnosis and treatment of diseases.

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